

Expressive Art Therapy: Efficacy Among Clients With Traumatic Brain Injury In Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 23, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 24, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Expressive Art Therapy, Traumatic Brain Injury, Depression</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6481701</p>	<p><i>The present study intended to investigate the role of expressive art therapy in dealing with depressive symptoms in survivors of traumatic brain injury. The study employed an experimental study design and Pretest Posttest Control Group Design was used in the study. Sample consisted of (n= 8) of which (n= 4) individuals were included in control group while (n= 4) were included in experimental group. Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (Hamilton, 1960) was used to assess depression at pre-intervention and post-intervention levels. Data was analyzed through Descriptive statistics, Reliability analysis, and Wilcoxon-Signed Rank Test. Expressive art therapy effectively reduces the symptoms of depression in patients of traumatic brain injury. Results also revealed that there is a significant difference in the reduction of symptoms of depression between the control group and the treatment group. The Control group presented less reduction in depression severity as compared to the treatment group. The overall conclusion of the study states that expressive art therapy is effective for dealing with depressive symptoms in men and women having a history of traumatic brain injury. The present study has wide implications for psychologists, medical practitioners, mental health institutes, patients, and different institutes working for the welfare of mental health patients.</i></p>

Introduction

Economic burden caused by Traumatic brain injury has been estimated at about \$400 billion at global level (van Dijeck et al., 2019). Traumatic brain injury is a disruption in functioning of brain that often requires an emergency case. The economic burden of Traumatic brain injury enhances for a developing country like Pakistan with an estimate of about \$22million dollar spent on emergency care annually, on average (Hussain et al., 2019). Pervez, Kitagawa, and Chang (2018) explained traumatic brain injury as an injury to the head caused by any external, mechanical force and which leads to a disturbance in the typical functioning of the brain. External force in this case was further explained as a blow, bump, or a jolt to head. Pathophysiological classification of traumatic brain injury involves primary and secondary traumatic brain injury. Primary traumatic brain injury is an anatomical or physiological injury which is often the result of direct impact. It involves direct mechanical trauma. In primary traumatic brain injury, there is almost a complete lack of functional repair. Secondary traumatic brain injury is most often caused by primary injury and it refers to somewhat avoidable damage that is presented after some time of the initial injury (Lazaridis et al., 2019). Hypoxia, hyponatremia, hypertension, and seizures are symptomatic of secondary brain injury. Secondary injury mechanisms also involve blood-brain barrier disruption, inflation, ion-mediated cell-damage, secondary hemorrhage, and ischemia among many others.

Traumatic brain injury is not only laid up with immediate clinical aspects but also comes with some delayed sequelae. Some psychological and physiological changes that are followed by traumatic brain injury are autonomic function alteration, loss of consciousness, disturbance in motor functioning, and ocular movement impairment (Gilbertson & Aldrige, 2008; Cho, 2016). Changes in autonomic functioning involve fracas in pulse rate, blood pressure, temperature, respiratory patterns, and salivation. Some other ramifications of TBI involve problems of cognition, psychological disturbance, and personality changes. Lack of concentration, information processing speed, and executive functions emanates after TBI. Insight is also disturbed after TBI (Rice et al., 2017). Psychological changes involve personality changes and prevailing personality disorders after TBI involve avoidant, borderline, or antisocial personality disorders. depression and anxiety also come under the umbrella of the sequelae of TBI. Aggression, emotional dysregulation, passivity, and mood swings are some other important emotional changes that are presented post-TBI. Behavioral changes after TBI involves loss of self-control, management problems, and uncertainty about the future. In their study, Koponen et al., (2006) discussed the rates of different psychiatric disorders after traumatic brain injury. Their study indicated that rates for post-TBI depression were 14%–77%, for dysthymia 2%–14%, bipolar disorder stands at 2%–17%. the 4%–17% for panic disorder (1, 8–10), 1%–10% for phobic disorders (8–10), 2%–15% findings for anxiety disorder

were also found. The most common of anxiety disorders after TBI was generalized anxiety disorder with a prevalence rate of 3%-28%, for panic disorder, it was 4%-17%, 2%-15% for OCD, 3%–27% for PTSD (Ahmed et al., 2017). Similarly, TBI induced psychosis also had an estimated prevalence of 1%. These prevalence rates implied that depression was a generic diagnosis after TBI

For dealing with the symptoms of traumatic brain injury, pharmacotherapy has been in use and is an evidence-based treatment. Yet, effective dealing of different psychological problems caused by traumatic brain injury can be accomplished through psychotherapies. Expressive art therapy, as a psychotherapy, is an integrative approach that serves the purpose of connecting other art processes and involves imagery, creativity, expressive writings, and art rituals to form a cohesive therapeutic approach (Lee & Kwon, 2020). Expressive art therapy is an amalgamated process that comprises of many different intervention strategies. It entangles imaginative expression to consolidated art processes (Kaimal et al., 2018). These art processes help to heal, give a sense of cognizance, helps to give a vivid understanding of one's psyche or soul. Malchiodi (2005) explicated expressive art as the use of different media including theater, expressive writing, sand tray, and play therapy in the milieu of therapeutic counseling, rehabilitation purposes, and general health care.

Expressive art therapy helps in the personal growth of an individual that occurs in terms of letting go of old unhealthy bad habits and to adopt new more competitive good and healthy habits. Edwards (2004) elucidated expressive art therapy as a "therapeutic approach that is viciously grounded in active imagination". He added further that spontaneous painting, drawing, and sculpting used in expressive art therapy is used to explore different facets of personality. Expressive art therapy aggravates the dormant creativity and unleashes hidden conflicts accompanying by a healing process. Artwork conjures aesthetic countertransference both from therapist and client (Hass-Cohen et al., 2018; Chiang et al., 2019). The artwork also evaluates the nature of the relationship a client and a therapist have. So, in this triangle all three axes exert their effective role in therapy sessions.

The theoretical background of expressive art therapy includes the Expressive therapy continuum also known as (ETC) proposed by Kagin and Lusebrink (1978). The expressive therapy continuum model focuses on the integration of information that is based upon neurological research evidence and it tries to define the way the brain works to process images and explain it in terms of sensory-motor development, psychosocial behavior patterns, self-psychology, and cognition. ETC talks about the creative expression at four different levels.

The object-relations approach to art therapy can be used to make known unfinished developmental stages (Klein, 2018). Art therapy facilitates the expression of hidden conflicts and helps to resolve early life relationship issues. Art therapy addresses interpersonal issues and attachment problems. Relationships with significant others might influence later personality traits (Klein, 2017). The use of art therapy in the context of the object relation approach offers a holding environment that allows the client to let go of unconscious pain and disturbing feelings (Heimann, 2018; Blomdahl et al., 2016). Modern attachment theory has highlighted a crucial point that although attachment patterns are developed in infancy or early life its impact can be altered later with some sort of therapeutic techniques (Holmes, 2014). Modern attachment theory has also emphasized the idea that the brain is quite adaptable and in the presence of optimal environmental conditions brain's functionality becomes most favorable (McTavish, 2018). Expressive art therapy thus plays a vital role in establishing new, secure attachment patterns and helps to resolve relationship conflicts with the help of artwork (Leavy, 2019).

Chapman (2014) postulated that the bilateral process of art therapy taps the subconscious and allows the client to actively process their art expression. Other researchers further explained that cognitive performance and executive functioning are quite enhanced through art therapy. Another important task of art therapy is to promote bilateral integration of the brain. The left brain responds to some verbal and factual information while the right brain is stimulated through art and non-verbal ideas (Hass-Cohen, 2016).

Researchers suggest that expressive art assists the clients to deal effectively with their psychological and health conditions and it also stipulates indispensable tidings about clients and their relationship problems (Haeyen&Hinz, 2020). Moreover, expressive art interventions also result in a tremendous decrease in the impact of a traumatic event, pain intensity, negative effect, and pain endorsement. Understanding of traumatic events was also increased post-intervention. Art therapy when used in combination with some other therapies tends to have positive outcomes in the sense that an amalgamation of verbal or talk therapies with nonverbal therapy provides a brief treatment that covers all important aspects of personality (Braddock, 2018). Any sort of abuse whether physical or psychological in childhood tends to cause gaps in the development of an individual and expressive art therapy helps to fill those gaps by targeting the conflicting issues by helping that individual. Expressive art as compared to cognitive nature type and other verbal therapies has an advantage of expressing the unfathomable and concealed conflicts. The conclusion of this research accentuated that expressive art therapy should be practiced gaining auxiliary insight into an individual's glitches (Kaimal et al., 2018; Hass-Cohen et al., 2018; Schouten et al., 2015; Chong, 2015).

The idiosyncratic nature of art incorporates different modalities that fallouts in the healing of traumatized individuals. The multimodal approach of expressive art therapy develops good coping skills,

resilience, and good effect (Lane, 2018). Art therapy is quite helpful in decreasing the pain and anxiety level of inpatients and it also helped in mood betterment. Moreover, art therapy sessions play the role of distraction from adverse health conditions which, in turn, invigorates patients thus ensuring better conditions (Kalmanowitz, 2016). A decline in GI conditions, epileptic patients' anxiety reduction, and mood improvement are also associated with expressive art therapy and it also helps in breakneck revival and restoration of health. Furthermore, expressive art could be equally useful for a wide range of patients with different backgrounds and without any prior training of art. An augmented cognizance of probable reimbursements of expressive therapies might aid to thwart the impending risk of psychopathology (Shella, 2018; Roddy et al., 2018).

The rationale of this study was to investigate the proficiency of expressive art therapy in the management of survivors of traumatic brain injury with major depressive disorder. The underlying drive to conduct this study is to alleviate mental health problems faced by individuals with sustained traumatic brain injury. Research on expressive art therapy is fabricated to let the participants of the study to delve into their inner self, to give way to their unexpressed, scrapping emotions and memories to emerge from the concealment of their unconscious mind. In this study effectiveness of art therapy in helping those individuals to do catharsis was checked. Besides, this study aimed to explore the therapeutic effect in the treatment of mental health problems. The primary hypothesis of the study was to check the impact of expressive art therapy in the reduction of symptoms of depression in patients with traumatic brain injury.

Method

The research was an experimental study and Pretest Posttest Control Group Design was used in the study. In the present study, a control group was defined and allocation to the control group was done. The other group was treatment group, and four participants were included in the group. Pretest and posttest were done at the start and the end of the therapy process. The Control group was provided with pharmacotherapy and conventional psychotherapeutic approached. Whiletreatment group was provided with expressive therapy interventions.

The sample was obtained from the outdoor facility of the Neurosurgery unit of General Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. In total, twelve individuals were selected initially including 8 men (66%) and four women (34%). They were selected according to the inclusion criteria, but of those fifteen only eight completed the therapy process. Equal distribution of males and females in control and treatment group was made in start of the therapy process. However, some attrition occurred in both groups. The mean age of participants of the experimental group was 34.25 years while the mean age of the participant in the experimental group was 33.5 years. All of the participants included in the treatment group and control group had a history of traumatic brain injury and also reported symptoms of depression such as fatigue, hopelessness, suicidal ideation, sleep problems, tension, headache, and loss of pleasure in daily activities.

Descriptive statistics included two groups i.e., treatment (50%) and control (50%) groups with a frequency of 4 each. There were three men and five women with a frequency percent of 37.5 and 62.5 respectively. Three age groups were formed in a study in which two participants lied in the 20-30 years age group, four participants lied in 21-40 years groups while two participants lied in the 41-50 years age group with a frequency percent of 25.0, 50.0, and 25.0 respectively. Five of the individuals lived in a joint family system while three of the participants lived in a nuclear family system which depicted a percentage of 62.5 and 37.5 respectively. Similarly, other demographics show the number of children and the number of siblings each participant had. Financial condition was also asked from participants and six (75%) of the participants responded as having a stable financial condition and two (25%) of the participants responded as having a non-stable condition.

Traumatic brain injury assessment sheet was used to assess about traumatic brain injury. Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (Hamilton, 1960) was also used in this study. This is a clinician-rated 21-item scale. After approval by the institute body of authority, research was started. Then, permission was taken from the Medical Superintendent of General Hospital and Head of the Department, Department of Neurosurgery, General Hospital. Clients were recruited from the therapy process from the outdoor facility of the hospital. Clients were recruited after screening for traumatic brain injury and symptoms of any psychological issue. Sessions with clients were taken over three months. In total, each client in the treatment group was given 12 sessions involving pretest and posttest sessions. Twelve sessions of control group participants were also taken and provided with psychoeducation, conventional psychotherapy and pharmacotherapy. After taking complete 12 sessions with treatment group participants, therapy was terminated.

In the treatment group, three women and one man were included and subsequently mentioned expressive art therapy protocol was followed. In the first session of expressive art therapy, the complete history of traumatic brain injury of clients was taken. Through behavioral observation, clinical interview, and the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale severity of depressive symptoms was assessed in the first session. Clients were also provided with an overview of expressive art therapy. In the second session, scribbling was done. In the third session, the Zen tangle was made by clients. Zen tangle provides a way to release stress through

drawing in specific shapes and also helps to increase focusing ability. In the fourth session, mandala drawing was done. In the fifth session, collage formation was done by the clients. Different collages were made by clients including animal collage, flower collage, nature collage, and motivational collage. In the sixth session, clients were asked to do finger painting. In the seventh session, clients were asked to make the color in the emotion wheel and then to give meaning to each color and consider the significance of colors in one's life. Some of the clients also made self-portrait which helps to identify emotions in one's body and its effect upon them. In the eighth session, the dreamcatcher was made by some of the clients while others made postcards. In the ninth session, miscellaneous expressive art activities were done by clients that involve coloring in the boundary, drawing with hollow space in the middle, and completing the incomplete figure through making something new out of it. In the tenth session, a worry box was made by some of the clients while some clients did make some drawings. In the eleventh session, clients were involved in sand drawing using a sand tray. In the twelfth session, Hamilton Depression Rating Scale was used to assess the symptoms of depression at the post-intervention level.

The Control group consisted of four participants of which two were men while two were women. The age of the participants of the control group was under the range of 20-40 years. Two participants suffered from severe traumatic brain injury while the other two suffered from moderate traumatic brain injury. Demographic information sheet, traumatic brain injury assessment sheet, and Hamilton Depression Rating Scale were also administered. Hamilton depression rating scale was again administered on participants of the control group after two months of initial administration. While doing the study it was made sure to abide by all ethical considerations.

Results and Discussion

First, reliability analysis of the Hamilton depression rating scale at the pretest and posttest level was done. The total number of items (K) of Hamilton Depression Rating Scale Pretest was 17 and the results indicated its mean as 27.25 with a standard deviation of 5.41. The analysis showed its skewness as .96 and Cronbach's alpha value for Hamilton Depression Rating Scale-Pretest is .73. This value of Cronbach's α is indicative of fair reliability of scale Potential range of the scale is different for different items. For items of depressed mood, frequency of guilt, suicide, work activities, retardation, agitation, psychic anxiety, somatic anxiety, and hypochondriasis potential range consists of 0-4 Likert scale. Early, middle/ late insomnia, somatic symptoms, insight, and loss of weight items have a potential range of 0-2. The actual range of the pretest was 21-39 while the actual range of the post-test was 11-32. Further, the reliability analysis of the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale-Posttest was also done. Reliability analysis showed that Hamilton Depression Rating Scale Posttest has 17 number of items (K) with a mean of 17.26 and a standard deviation of 6.81. The skewness of the scale is 1.7 and the value of Cronbach's alpha was .75 which indicates that the scale's reliability is good.

Wilcoxon-Signed Rank Test on Symptoms of Depression at Pre-Intervention and Post-Intervention Level

Variables	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	z	sig
Depression	4.50	36.00	-2.53	.011
Depressed mood	4.50	36.00	-	2.55.011
Feelings of guilt	1.50	3.00	-1.41	.021
Suicide	3.50	21.00	-2.33	.020
Insomnia: early	2.50	10.00	-1.89	.059
Insomnia: middle	2.50	10.00	-2.00	.046
Insomnia: late	2.50	10.00	-1.89	.059
Work and activities	3.50	21.00	-2.33	.020
Retardation	3.00	15.00	-2.12	.034
Agitation	2.00	4.00	.577	.041
Anxiety: somatic	3.00	15.00	-2.0	.038
Anxiety: psychic	3.50	21.00	-2.33	.020
Gastrointestinal symptoms	2.50	10.00	-2.00	.046
General somatic symptoms	1.50	3.00	-1.34	.032
General symptoms	2.00	6.00	-1.73	.03
Hypochondriasis	2.00	6.00	-1.63	.02
Loss of weight	1.50	3.00	-1.34	.03
Insight	2.00	6.00	-1.73	.083

Results of the Wilcoxon-Signed Rank test shows significant difference in total scores of depression scale before and after expressive art intervention, $z(8) = -2.53, p < 0.05$. Results also indicated a significant difference in depressed mood before and after therapy, $z(8) = -2.58, p < 0.05$. Feelings of guilt also showed a significant difference before and after therapy with $z(8) = -1.41, p < 0.05$. Results reveal that difference in early insomnia is significant, $z(8) = -1.89, p < 0.05$. Middle insomnia and late insomnia also showed significant

difference, $z(8) = -2.00, p < 0.05$; $z(8) = -1.89, p < 0.05$ values respectively. Significant difference was also found in work and activities routine before and after therapy, $z(8) = -2.33, p < 0.05$. Before and after therapy retardation also indicated a significant difference, $z(8) = -2.12, p < 0.05$. Before and after therapy score of agitation showed a significant difference, $z(8) = .56, p = .41$. Psychic anxiety depicted a significant difference before and after therapy, $z(8) = -2.33, p < 0.05$. Somatic anxiety was also reduced with a difference of $z(8) = -2.7, p < 0.05$. Gastrointestinal symptoms also indicated a significant difference in both pre-intervention and post-intervention scores $z(8) = -2.0, p < 0.05$. General somatic symptoms showed no significant difference before and after therapy $z(8) = -1.34, p = .032$. General symptoms showed a significant difference in before and after scores, $z(8) = -1.73, p < 0.05$. Hypochondriasis and loss of weight showed no significant difference before and after therapeutic intervention with $z(8) = -1.63, p = .02$; $z(8) = -1.34, p = .03$ values respectively. Insight depicted significant difference before and after therapeutic intervention $z(8) = -1.73, p < 0.05$.

The study was designed to investigate the efficacy of expressive art therapy among clients with traumatic brain injury. In the study, symptomatology of depression was assessed in clients with traumatic brain injury. Expressive art therapy interventions were implemented to see any alterations in the depressive symptoms of clients with traumatic brain injury. It was hypothesized that expressive art therapy would likely to reduce symptoms of depression in individuals with traumatic brain injury. For this purpose, Wilcoxon-Signed Rank Test was used to analyze the data. Results of this data analysis suggested that significant difference occurs in pre-intervention and post-intervention rating of depressive systems of patients on the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (Hamilton, 1960). Results also indicated that symptoms of depression were reduced after applying expressive art techniques.

Conclusion

It is concluded that expressive art therapy is effective in dealing with the symptomatology of depression among clients with traumatic brain injury. The significant difference in the pre-intervention and post-intervention rating of symptoms of depression on the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale among clients with traumatic brain injury is suggestive of the fact that expressive therapy affects the lives of individuals to a significant level and leaves its long-term embosses on those individuals who practiced it at any stage of their life. This study concludes that, in such cases, expressive art therapy plays an essential role in dealing with psychological problems and in lessening of physical pains. This study further proposes a conclusion that along with medication, expressive art therapy results in speedy recovery from physical and psychological ailments thus enhancing life-satisfaction and changing life perspective. Other results also indicated that expressive art therapy also aids in dealing with problems of sad mood, suicidal thoughts, and somatic symptoms. Moreover, it also helps to reduce gastrointestinal symptoms, insomnia, and sexual problems. As it helps to improve mood it also helps with the problem of excessive weeping in depression. The results of this study lead to the conclusion that expressive art therapy is an effective treatment for dealing with depression after traumatic brain injury along with pharmacotherapy. Results also indicate that individuals only having pharmacotherapy for their depressive symptoms after traumatic brain injury reported late recovery and less change in the severity of depression, while individuals on pharmacotherapy and art therapy reported a significant difference in their severity level of depression. The overall conclusion of the study strongly suggests that expressive art therapy is very effective for dealing with psychological problems after traumatic brain injury.

This research will be beneficial for the psychologists, mental health practitioners, medical practitioners, participants, and families of the participants. This study also has strong implication for researchers who wants to explore new methods to deal with psychological problems presented with physical ailments. This therapy proved the efficacy of expressive art therapy which also opens new avenues of research in this field.

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